

A STUDY OF SYNONYMY OF ALLIED AND NON-ALLIED COMPLEX SENTENCES

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Annotation: *The article is devoted to the problem of synonymy of form and sense. According to the present scientific trends it is important to analyze the synonyms from the position of anthropocentrism, asymmetry, symmetry and integration.*

Key words: *synonymy, synonymy of forms, synonymy of senses, theoretical model, integration, criterions*

ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ СИНОНИМИИ СОЮЗНЫХ И БЕССОЮЗНЫХ СЛОЖНЫХ ПРЕДЛОЖЕНИЙ

Аннотация *Статья посвящена проблеме синонимии формы и смысла. Согласно существующим научным тенденциям важно проанализировать синонимы от положения антропоцентризма, асимметрии, симметрии и интеграции.*

Ключевые слова: *синонимия, синонимия форм, синонимия смыслов, теоретическая модель, интеграция, критерии*

The study of synonymy, which is one of the universal semantic constants of natural language, is of great importance for modern science in general methodological and practical terms. From a methodological point of view, the problem of synonymy is inseparable from the question of the connection between language, thinking and reality, identity and difference, symmetry and asymmetry, identifying the place and diversity of language functions in the process of cognition and communication. In practical terms, the consideration of this problem is determined by the important role of a person's possession of synonymous means, which make it possible to choose from the dictionary and grammatical system of the language precisely those means that accurately express his thoughts and feelings. It is the methodological and practical significance of the problems of synonymy, associated with understanding the problems of communication and cognition, that makes the study of synonymic

relations in language especially relevant within the framework of the linguistic paradigm of the late 20th and early 21st centuries with a clearly marked turn towards a comprehensive study of objects in language and language as a whole.

The prospects for an integrated approach to the language, focusing not on particulars, but on the integrity and nature of the integrative interaction of its parts, put forward a number of new and actualized some of the already known problems in linguistics. These include the identification of the correlation of linguistic and mental categories, the definition of general and particular patterns of implementation of language units in a comprehensive analysis of the universal semantic constants of the language: polysemy, homonymy, conversion, antonymy.

The problem of synonymy, despite a long history of study in different paradigms of linguistic knowledge and comprehension at different levels of the language system with varying degrees of effectiveness, has not yet become the subject of a comprehensive analysis. However, synonymy as a semantic interaction of the identity and difference of linguistic units has been most fully studied at the word level in connection with a systematic approach to lexical units. A large number of works on the material of various languages are devoted to its study, criteria for its description are identified, and its theoretical and practical purpose is determined. And the results of numerous studies of the problem under discussion are recorded in synonymous dictionaries. In grammatical science, the problem of synonymy was developed mainly in morphology, in syntax this problem has not been studied exhaustively, which is primarily due to the fact that syntax (the study of scientific syntax, which was initiated by A.M.

Peshkovsky began to develop much later than vocabulary and morphology. The ideas of the theory of transformational grammar and the doctrine of syntactic transposition gave impetus to the development and beginning of the study of syntactic synonymy. At the same time, in the study of the problem of synonymy, tasks were set and solved within the framework of one, separately taken level of the language. Meanwhile, a clear delimitation of the levels of the language system in the analysis of synonymy, in addition to unconditional advantages, has its drawbacks. More G.W.F. Hegel wrote about the meaning of the whole for the parts of the organism: "Their living unity is not indifferent to them, but, on the contrary, it is a substance in which and through which they can only preserve their own individuality".

New perspectives in the study of synonymy are associated with the study of the functioning of synonymic units in the text, which led to the formulation and study of the problem of synonymy at the text level.

The experience of the previous study of synonymy, the tendency of a not too rigid distinction between lexical, morphological and syntactic synonymy, the inclusion of synonymy in the broad range of problems of semantic studies of the language has

prepared by now the foundation for creating a theoretical model for analyzing the integrative interaction of synonymous units of the same and different levels of affiliation, within which it can be an objective and complex picture of synonymic relations in the language is obtained. One of the theoretical settings of the model for analyzing the integrative interaction of synonymous units of the same and different levels of belonging is the description of synonymy as one of the semantic constants of natural language, closely related to the essence of a person, his worldview, spiritual and practical activities.

Since it is impossible to describe synonymic relations in a language in isolation from a person whose essence "... rests in the language", the human factor is chosen as a system-forming link when discussing the problem of synonymy. The next setting in the development of a theoretical model for the analysis of the integrative interaction of synonymous units of the same and different levels of belonging is to determine the essence and nature of the concept of synonymy in close connection with the logical and philosophical doctrines of identity.

This made it necessary to involve representatives of the mainly German logical-philosophical tradition as key works, distinguished by self-sufficiency when it comes to developing problems of identity. As reference points, the principle of the identity of the indistinguishable (Leibniz 1983), the aporia of identity and difference by I. Kant, the interaction of identity and difference by G.V.F. Hegel, which are complemented by the concepts of symmetry and asymmetry, which are integral attributes of the language system, the real world and human nature as an integral part of this world. The principle of symmetry and the principle of asymmetry of the form and content of language units underlie the existence of synonymy, the essence of which is that the same content has several forms for its expression. If symmetry is a manifestation of balance and static, then asymmetry is a manifestation of movement, various transformations caused by shifts and rotations of objects in space and time, as well as their combinations. The use of the principle of symmetry and the principle of asymmetry makes it possible to include the spatio-temporal parameters inherent in all processes occurring in the world, from the simple movement of objects in space and time to thinking, into the definition of identity and difference.

An essential, if not exclusive, role in the analysis of synonymous relations between linguistic units in this model is given to the use of the theoretical development of G. Frege of two interrelated concepts – "meaning" and "meaning", related to the subject and semantic content of linguistic expressions. The theoretical development of the relationship between meaning and meaning is expanded by the description of the meaning of linguistic expressions proposed by W. Quine through a set of synonymous transformations. Their use significantly expands the analysis and

makes possible a constructive study of synonymy, which in the proposed model is carried out in two directions.

On the one hand, various linguistic forms were subjected to synonymic analysis and what was common between them was determined, according to the method of describing the meaning of linguistic expressions proposed in a number of semantic works of the logical-philosophical and linguistic directions: the meaning of a linguistic expression is the class of all linguistic expressions that are synonymous with data. On the other hand, a search was carried out and the establishment of another concept of the content of synonyms - the meaning of synonymous units. The bidirectional study of synonymic relations between linguistic units brings the analysis of synonymy beyond the language in the direction from the synonymy of forms to the synonymy of meanings, which significantly expands the theoretical model for the analysis of the integrative interaction of synonyms of the same and different levels of belonging.

Since the study of language and synonymy as one of the most important semantic constants of a language is connected with the essence of a person and his attitude to the world around him and to himself, the study of the problem of synonymy required an expansion of theoretical development. In this case, we are talking about the inclusion in the circle of objects of reference, limited in logic and analytical philosophy and in most linguistic works to objects, phenomena, events of extralinguistic reality, a person as a carrier of information about external reference. This corresponds to the general philosophical position that a person belongs to the natural objects of the real world. The speaker, describing a reference external to him, appropriates the formal apparatus of language and, with the help of it, manifests his position, forming the center of internal reference. This explains the introduction of the concept of "internal reference" into the development of a theoretical model for the analysis of synonymy. Therefore, one can speak of a reference external to the speaker and at the same time internal as the speaker's attitude to it. Internal reference is a reflection in the semantics of linguistic expressions of all human introspections, defined as the semantics of the speaker's personal partiality to the reported. The reflection of a common reference in linguistic units that are in relation to synonymy coincides, they are semantically identical to each other. The reflection of the internal reference does not coincide, they are semantically different. On the dialectical unity of semantic identity and difference, the synonymy of language units of varying complexity and syntactic configuration (words, morphemes, phrases, sentences, texts) is based, which have the same type of correlation with external reference and differ in the speaker's personal bias towards it. If the description of the synonymy of linguistic units stopped at the analysis of the synonymy of forms, then the path to a complete and adequate picture of synonymous relations in the language would be closed, reflecting the interaction of denotative and connotative meanings (emotionally expressive and

evaluative), stylistic, register, social, territorial, professionally specialized differences between synonyms.

As a result of the analysis of the factual material on the basis of the methodological guidelines adopted in this model, it was revealed that the objective reality in which synonyms function is the text as a product of the speaker's verbal and mental activity. The functioning of synonyms in the text is subordinated to the creation of the semantic integrity of the text, based on the unity of the theme, provided by the identity of the reference, the correlation throughout the text with the same fragment of the extralinguistic reality of synonymic units. At the same time, it is fundamentally important to analyze not individual synonyms, but the totality of synonyms in their relationship to each other in the process of functioning in the text. In this regard, the work clarifies the concept of a synonymic series as a system of symmetrical and asymmetric in form and content of language units, which significantly expanded the idea of a synonymic series by including linguistic units of different levels. All of the above allows us to state that the proposed model of synonymous relations of linguistic units clearly shows that synonymy as one of the universal semantic constants, along with other semantic constants of natural language, is one of the possible options for explaining complex, multi-parametric relationships between language, thought and reality. This model reflects numerous information processes that occur in the mind of a person when he creates a certain conceptual picture of the surrounding reality. Theoretically constructive and methodologically important is also the conclusion that the integrative interaction of synonymous units of the same-level and multi-level belonging can be one of the processes leading to the acquisition and consolidation of new knowledge. As a result, we have a methodologically sound and promising model for describing the synonymous relations of linguistic units, applicable to the analysis not only of a single natural language, but also when comparing languages within the framework of interlingual synonymy.

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